

THE MECHANISM FOR PERFORMING A SOCIALLY DANGEROUS ACTION
AS A PREDICTOR OF THE RISK OF RELAPSE

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Abstract. *The literature, which focuses on the problem of preventing a socially dangerous act, focuses heavily on the study of the mechanisms of criminal prosecution of the mentally ill. Researchers unanimously agree that the mechanism of social risky action plays an important role in identifying and predicting the risk factors of repeated social risky action. The mechanism of social risky action is a mandatory component of the social risk formula, and therefore, in each case, its study is an integral part of the preventive system.*

Key words: *Prevention, prognosis, factor, risk of recurrence.*

МЕХАНИЗМ ВЫПОЛНЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНО ОПАСНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ КАК
ПРЕДИКТОР РИСКА РЕЦИДИВА

Аннотация. *В литературе, посвященной проблеме предотвращения общественно опасного деяния, большое внимание уделяется изучению механизмов уголовного преследования психически больных. Исследователи единогласно сходятся во мнении, что механизм социального рискованного действия играет важную роль в выявлении и прогнозировании факторов риска повторного социального рискованного действия. Механизм социального рискованного действия является обязательной составляющей формулы социального риска, а потому в каждом конкретном случае его изучение является неотъемлемой частью профилактической системы.*

Ключевые слова: *Профилактика, прогноз, фактор, риск рецидива.*

Introduction. The problem of recurrence of crimes is one of the most complex and pressing in modern criminology. Recidivists form an important part of the criminal environment

and pose the main threat to public order and security [1]. Therefore, the study of the causes, conditions and mechanisms for the repeated occurrence of crimes is of important theoretical and practical importance. One such mechanism is the mechanism by which a socially dangerous act is performed, that is, the method, techniques and tools that the criminal uses to achieve his goal [2]. The mechanism for performing a socially dangerous act reflects the individual characteristics of the personality of the offender, his motives, goals, plans, skills and skills, as well as the influence of external factors such as the situation, victim, partners, etc. a mechanism for performing a socially dangerous action can be used as a criterion to assess the level of risk of the offender and the likelihood of his relapse [3].

The prognosis of the behavior of patients after the end of compulsory treatment and their level of social risk are directly related to the entire complex of socio-personal and clinical-psychopathological characteristics. Repeated offenses often occur according to negative-personal mechanisms, it is these patients who increase social risk, respectively, the role of this indicator as a predictive factor is greater. And studying it in different ways is of great importance in this regard [4].

The illegal behavior of individuals with mental disorders affects the state of Public Health and the social well-being of society as a whole. Cases in which socially dangerous behavior is committed by them are often seen as one of the indicators of low efficiency in the functioning of the psychiatric service, the competence of which includes their warning [5]. In recent years, the media has repeatedly extensively covered resonant offenses involving individuals under the supervision of a psychiatrist. Taking into account the relevance of the problem, it was devoted to the issue of interagency cooperation of law enforcement agencies and medical organizations in solving it [6].

The level of social danger of citizens of this category, in comparison with general population indicators, is heterogeneous in understanding various specialists, which is primarily associated with the polymorphism of mental pathology [7-9]. At first glance, the thesis that illegal behavior is more common among the mentally ill compared to generally accepted indicators does not raise doubts about their confirmation by the proportion between offenders in prison [10-12].

However, in this case we are talking about mild to moderately severe mental disorders. Qualified psychiatric care for them is one of the components of a set of measures to prevent the recurrence of criminal behavior based on interagency cooperation with the penal system, the priority of law enforcement agencies and Educational, Labor and social protection institutions [13-15].

In addition, in cases where dangerous behavior is associated with the presence of a mental illness in a patient, its severity (severity) determines that he cannot realize or control the true nature and social danger of his actions (inaction), the role and responsibility of the psychiatric service in its prevention is significantly increased [16, 17]. The reasons for the illegal behavior of mentally healthy criminals and individuals with severe mental disorders are different: the first is based on socio-psychological factors, the second is based on psychopathological factors, making criminological methods of anticipating and preventing it unsuitable, putting the solution of these problems in the competence of general psychiatric practice and forensic psychiatric examination activities [18].

Identifying a potential social risk is part of the daily practical activities of psychiatric service professionals, regardless of the service unit in which they work [19]. For example, forensic psychiatrists should make such assessments when making recommendations on the appointment and selection of the type of mandatory measures of a medical nature, determining whether the mental illness present in the patient is associated with the possibility of "causing other serious harm or danger to himself or others."persons" [20]. A local psychiatrist should measure the risk of socially dangerous behavior in cases where a serious mental disorder causes the patient to be able to perform aggressive or autoaggressive actions, as well as in solving issues of applying non-mandatory psychiatric measures when establishing an active dispensary observation of the patient. The duties of a psychiatrist working in a hospital include addressing the issue of whether or not to maintain the potential social risk of a patient undergoing mandatory treatment, as this determines the possibility of canceling or extending this treatment [21]. Psychiatric service personnel need reliable methods of assessing the risk of dangerous behavior of people with mental disorders to help them make expert and clinical decisions. In this regard, specialists from many countries are conducting scientific research aimed at identifying the causes of socially dangerous behavior and looking for informative ways to predict it [22-24].

Risk factors and approaches to social risk assessment the scientific community has collected more material on risk factors for socially risky actions. Foreign researchers have statistical significance: age; problems of personality formation, early criminalization, the presence of experience in participating in violent actions; lack of housing; social disruption; material problems; low educational level; unfavorable social environment; as a result of creating a negative environment around an individual with mental illness, including a reassessment of risk to society [25]. The most important reasons that determine the increased risk of dangerous actions are non-

compliance with the treatment regimen and Substance Use, as well as the violence experienced [26].

The recognized risk factor for dangerous behavior is the pathological warehouse of the individual, the presence of such characteristics as aggression, stiffness, excitability, vindictiveness [27]. Depending on the approach taken as a basis in a particular research work on the assessment of risk factors, the authors distinguish between their different number and different groups. For example, a study initiated by the MacArthur Foundation examined more than a hundred factors for risk assessment [28].

J. According to Monahan, the best predictors of the manifestation of violence among the mentally ill are the same factors as a group of mentally healthy criminals; one of the weakest risk factors is the diagnosis [29]. This view was taken by J. Bonta et al. [30], argued that important criteria for predicting the risk of risky behavior towards nosological affiliation were factors such as past violence, alcoholism or drug abuse, and family problems. However, other foreign researchers have pointed out that there is a relationship between the frequency of violent crimes and a specific psychiatric diagnosis [31].

As the main local scientific concepts that define the dangerous behavior of the mentally ill, the following can be distinguished: the concept of a triad of factors-"syndrome-personality-situation" [32] and the concept of psychopathological mechanisms of socially dangerous actions [33]. They are based on the recognition of the importance of psychopathological and situational factors in the genesis of social danger, as well as the individual characteristics of the patient in their interaction. In particular, the concept of a psychopathological mechanism of socially dangerous actions is defined as "the interaction of mental disorders with each other, as well as with personal and situational factors that determine the action in question and exclude the possibility of interpreting it as a crime" [34]. Several attempts have been made by scientists to assess the potential risk of the mentally ill [35]. At the same time, it was proposed to derive from a number of clinical and social psychological characteristics that characterize one or another patient. This, in particular, implied anamnestic data on the direction of his social activity, the degree of adaptation to social and labor, personal characteristics. Independent importance was attached to the nature of socially dangerous actions and especially the clinical manifestations and dynamics of the disease. A comprehensive analysis of this data was proposed to identify and quantify two indicators: the weight and probability of the predicted Action [36]. Taking into account its assessment in the scores on the two parameters considered, the general index of the patient's public risk is expressed as an arithmetic average between them. With the simplicity of this approach, it was not widely

used, perhaps due to a number of questions raised by experts about the possibility of performing socially dangerous actions and the lack of clear criteria for judging the severity of the predicted risky actions, especially in patients who have not previously performed them [37-40].

The practice that exists in our country is mainly based on the use of a clinical approach, in which psychiatrists assess the likelihood of patients taking risky actions using individual clinical characteristics, choosing risk factors based on their knowledge and experience. Such an assessment largely depends on the professional imagination, level of training and clinical experience of the specialist, and the personality of the patient, the conditions for its formation, other anamnestic data and situational factors are not always analyzed in decision-making. Such a definition of potential social risk does not always ensure the objectivity and accuracy of the forecast [41-43].

This is evidenced by the results of multi-year monitoring of the data of the State Statistical Report. For example, the number of an active dispensary surveillance team, the duration of mandatory treatment, the recurrence rates of dangerous actions in a number of regions of the country differ several times from the average Russian indicator, which indicates that there are problems in determining the risk of dangerous behavior of people with mental disorders [44-47].

There are conflicting opinions about the use of unstructured clinical assessment to decide on the potential risk of the patient – possible subjectivity of specialists, the presence of differences in their preparation and clinical experience, the desire to "reinsure" and "re-evaluate" risk risk, insufficient criteria, the impossibility of reconstructing the decision-making process and checking [48-50].

The purpose of this study was to study the clinical-social characteristics of patients with negative-personal and productive-psychotic mechanisms of performing a socially dangerous action, to identify factors that contribute to the implementation of a socially dangerous action in socially dangerous patients in order to develop criteria for predicting their behavior after the end of mandatory treatment.

Research materials and methods. The study was conducted on the basis of the Department of compulsory treatment of a specialized psychiatric clinical hospital. During 2022-2023, a permanent sample of patients undergoing compulsory treatment was conducted at this hospital. a total of 74 people were examined, of which 40 (54%) patients performed socially dangerous behaviors under negative-personal mechanisms (Group 1) and 34 (46%) effective-psychotic (Group 2). comparisons). All those examined are men. The criteria for joining the study were the presence of a confirmed severe mental illness, which deprived the patient of the ability

to be aware of or manage the true nature and social danger of their actions. The leading method of research was clinical and psychopathological.

The research scheme the first stage of the study is devoted to the identification of the peculiarities of self-control, self-control and social apperception, as well as the study of the clinical, social and pathopsychological characteristics of mental patients who performed repeated socially dangerous actions and were undergoing mandatory treatment. To accomplish this goal, a comparison of the parameters under study was made between individuals who performed one-time social risk actions and individuals who performed repeated social risk actions using the χ^2 criterion for nominative data and the Mann–Whitney U-criterion for metric.

In the second stage, subpopulations of patients were identified, depending on their nosological dependence, in order to determine the specifics of the psychological structure of self-control, self-control and social apperception, in people with negative mental disorders of the individual, without taking into account the recurrence of socially dangerous actions committed. The data obtained in the two nosological groups was compared using Mann–Whitney's important difference criteria, using the crosstabulation method to analyze nominative indicators. Then, within each nosological group, the separation of subjects by the multiplicity of socially dangerous actions was carried out.

In the third stage of the study, patients who performed repeated socially dangerous actions were divided into small groups based on the level of social risk. A Discriminant Analysis was conducted to determine the contribution of disorders in the psychological structure of self-regulation and social apperception to increasing the risk of repeated socially dangerous behaviors by individuals with negative-personal mental disorders.

Experimental-psychological research method data has also been used. For systematization and statistical processing of the results obtained, a specially developed map and a software package SPSS 11,5 were used. In each of the groups, the frequency distribution of properties, their comparison were analyzed.

Research results. The age composition groups selected turned out to be relatively uniform, with the median age of patients committing socially dangerous behaviors being 37 years in the first group and 44 years in the second. As a result of the study, significant differences in many social, clinical and biological parameters were obtained between a group of patients with negative-personal and productive-psychotic mechanisms of socially dangerous action, which made it possible to identify signs of unfavorable prognosis of patient behavior after mandatory treatment. In the majority of those examined (96,2%), a variety of characteristic deviations were reported in

the premorbid, of which unstable features were significantly superior in both groups (57,5% and 44,1%, respectively).

At the time of the examination, the social status, the level of quality of life were lower for a group of patients with negative-personal mechanisms.

According to the nosological composition, patients of the studied groups are divided as follows. In the first group, patients with mental retardation (55%) are more common, and in the second group, people with schizophrenia (64,7%) are more common. The continuous type of disease dominated both groups, but it was more typical for patients with negative-personal mechanisms (87,5%). The first group was dominated by psychopathic-like (37,5%) as the main syndrome, while the second group was dominated by hallucinator-paranoid (64,7%).

At the time of the occurrence of socially dangerous behavior, the duration of the disease is mainly more than 15 years in the first and second groups. It should be added that alcohol played a certain inflammatory role in the commission of a socially dangerous act and was one of the leading factors contributing to their occurrence (67,5% and 61,8% in groups). Attention should be paid to the high percentage (51,3%) of individuals in the first group who previously committed socially dangerous behavior. The corresponding percentage of the second group is 32,4%, which indicates the high importance of the mechanism for performing a socially dangerous action as a factor for predicting relapse.

The first group was dominated by the high number of socially dangerous movements (27,5% performed 2 or more socially dangerous movements).

At the first stage of the study, the following distinctive features of the psychological structure of self-management of individuals with mental pathology, which performed repeated socially dangerous actions, were identified: insufficient functioning of the regulatory system, manifested in a violation of the ability to set goals and establish a program of actions to achieve goals, as well The violation of the ability to model important external and internal conditions for carrying out activities is manifested based on subjective criteria, in a limited understanding of the context of the situation, in ignoring the nuances of the relationship between the characters, in the production of a small number of alternative options for resolving the situation and in the inability to clearly distinguish.

Among the structures of self-management of patients who performed repeated socially dangerous actions, High indicators of preference for physical activity and the advantages of simple tasks in activity were significantly distinguished. Also, the group of individuals who performed

repeated socially dangerous actions was characterized by a high degree of manifestation of negative symptoms, if patients underestimated its severity.

Among the clinical-psychopathological and pathopsychological characteristics in patients with negative personality disorders who have repeatedly committed socially dangerous behavior, the following characteristics are noted: the previous age of the first socially dangerous actions, the predominance of aggressive crimes against the individual and the psychopathological mechanism for the implementation of socially dangerous actions – lack of high emotions ($p=0,02$), alcohol abuse ($p=0,011$), impairment of criticality in the broadest sense ($p=0,00$), low volume of information and knowledge ($p=0,00$).

To identify specific risk factors for violence, the differences between the studied variables in groups of patients with schizophrenia and organic mental disorders were analyzed. The results of the analysis of data from pathopsychological studies through the analysis of conjugation tables made it possible to determine the exact cognitive decline in 83% of patients with organic mental illness and 28% of patients with schizophrenia. In 70% of people with schizophrenia, there was an adequate development of the cognitive sphere and specific disorders of the thinking and emotional-voluntary sphere with a sufficient amount of information and knowledge. Most patients in both nosological groups were characterized by a significant decrease in critical and prognostic abilities (schizophrenia – 66,6%, organic mental illness – 82,3%).

Analysis of the data obtained using psychometric methods made it possible to identify specific characteristics for patients with organic mental illness who performed repeated socially dangerous actions. This is, in particular, an understanding of the main meaning of the situation in the absence of the ability to perceive the nuances of the relationship between the characters, which, in addition to a decrease in the ability to program and set goals, made it difficult to choose the best option for solving the situation in this group.

The choice of non-constructive options for solving the problem of these patients was associated with low self-control, which was manifested by preference for simple tasks in activity, risk, egocentrism and impulsivity.

Difficulties were found in understanding the context of a particular situation with a decrease in goal setting and programming ability in patients with schizophrenia who repeated socially dangerous behaviors. The subjective meaning introduced by patients in their interpretation of the situation has helped them choose socially acceptable ways to solve the problem, which are not context-sensitive but.

Analysis of the sample, separated by nosological affiliation and the abundance of socially dangerous actions committed, showed that patients with schizophrenia who performed repeated socially dangerous actions also have affective instability, impulsivity and egocentrism, which are low signs of self-control.

Clinical and psychological characteristics were dominated by delays in early development, Affective Disorders in the premorbid period, as well as the occurrence of socially dangerous actions in a drunken state.

Patients with organic mental illness who performed repeated socially dangerous behaviors were characterized by low indicators on all scales of self-control, chronic alcoholism, social disorder, the predominance of the selfish and selfish-violent direction of socially dangerous actions carried out by them.

When dividing patients into groups, an increase in the proportion of serious crimes against the individual was found among patients receiving compulsory treatment in a specialized institution with intensive observation, depending on the type of mandatory treatment that is carried out against them. Most of the re-enacted social risk acts were committed within 2 years of the cancellation of previous mandatory treatment, with more than a quarter of repeat crimes occurring during the first year. It should be noted that in 67,4% of cases, repeated violations were committed by such patients who were drunk.

According to the results of A Discriminant Analysis, important pathopsychological and psychological variables for distinguishing patients who have committed repeated socially dangerous behaviors according to the level of social risk are: violation of the criticality of the state of illness and socially dangerous actions in a broad sense; low development of the emotional-voluntary sphere; decrease in the level of generalization; decrease in

Conclusions. Thus, when assessing the prognosis of repeated socially dangerous behavior, discharge of patients from a hospital of a specialized type, it is necessary to take into account the totality of socio-personal and clinical-psychopathological characteristics. At the same time, as risk factors, the most important are: negative premorbid characteristics, the social status of patients - their professional, labor and family adaptation, situational factors in the form of increased alcoholism of patients; negative in the structure of the disease-the predominance of psychopathic-like changes with personal mechanisms and a constant progradative course; a short interval of recurrence in patients with repeated violations. During the period of compulsory treatment, an unstable mental state and a tendency to disrupt the regime should also be taken into account.

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